

**USING EXAMPLES OF CHILDREN'S PROSE TO REVEAL THE
CREATIVE ABILITIES OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS****Sultonova Gulasal Shodmonovna**

Master of BukhSPI II stage

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10663207>

The story is a minor form of the epic type. The story usually covers one (sometimes several interrelated events that took place over a short period of time) from the life of the hero. The short duration of the depicted events requires that the story is small in size, the plot is simple, and the number of participating characters is small. Not every story is a story. The event underlying the story needs to be complete and complete, for this it must have its own beginning and end (for example, as in an anecdote). Based on the description of the overall event, the storyteller reveals the essence of the event or the character through it. So, a story is a small artistic work, in which a certain event in a person's life, important aspects of life are summarized. A story often describes an event in a person's life. Its content is more vital than that of a fairy tale.

In the lesson of reading a story, it is also important to explain the meaning of words and phrases that students do not understand, otherwise they will not be able to understand the content of the story. Without spending a lot of time explaining the meaning of the word, it is explained with a short explanation of the word that is most necessary for explaining the content of the work.

In the process of working with the text, in order for the students to master the story well, to learn the idea presented in it, they should read it selectively, re-read it with a specific task, answer questions, make up a question for the story part themselves, etc. With z, all types of work are used, such as graphic drawing, planning, retelling, preparation for expressive reading.

For example, the hero of M. Murodov's story "The Boy Who Ate the Airplane" is a 2-3-year-old boy named Khoran. Because "He put everything in his mouth, his parents only brought him food. But one day, when he entered a toy store, he insisted that he would bring a toy airplane. Dad:

"This toy won't be for you," he said, but he took it anyway.

Khoran played the plane for three days. On the fourth day, he returned from the street empty-handed, without toys. Then, no matter how much his father and mother ask him, he is still a child

it means "I ate it". Out of concern, they called "Ambulance" and rushed to the hospital; "Aunt doctor" gently puts the child on a wooden bed, rubs and squeezes his stomach. When they asked, "Does it hurt?", even though it didn't

hurt, the child cried out of fear. His mother panicked again. Khoran cried even more when he entered the X-ray room because he was afraid. After the X-ray did not show any plane, when he returned home, his parents started asking again:

- Tell me the truth, did you really eat the plane?

"I was," Khoran said, crying. Khoran's mother angrily shouted slapped him on the back. The child cried. Then the teacher's neighbors came in and found out about the incident.

"You should ask the child without hitting or threatening him," he said, stroking Khoran's head and gently asking:

- My white boy, Khoranjan, tell me, did you swallow your plane whole or did you destroy it?

- I didn't win, I didn't break it.

- How did you eat?

- I changed it to Karim's ball.

- Where is the ball?

- I changed it to Salim's rifle.

- Where is the rifle?

- I changed it to a cake.

- Where is the cake?

"I ate it," Khoran said.

"Shall I tell you about the boy who ate the plane?" to younger students. just saying it turns their attention. That is, if a child says that he can eat a plane at this age, they will believe it. In this sense, the children who listened to the story until the end should refrain from such mistakes, which are still repeated in themselves, or the expression of the adults' attitude towards the children determines its educational nature, while the dialogue in the form of a return and the symbolism of the hero's name provided enjoyment. Similarly, in the story "Morning Word" by R. Farhodi, a number of imitation words are used: "Meow-meow! Huh-huh. Rot, rot! Whoah Whoah Whoah! Gok-gok-gok! Ga-ga-ga!". It is known that the words of Ahmed's friends who woke up in the morning - the cat, the wind, the leopard, the goose and the ducks - "Hello!" Such examples educate children and give aesthetic pleasure. Only then will the artistic word grow from the bud and begin to write leaves.

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